

Advanced Secure Cloud Encrypted Platform for Internationally Orchestrated Solutions in Healthcare

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3 Status, Change History and Glossary

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Table 1: Status Change History

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Table 2: Deliverable Change History

Glossary

ATF	Arm Trusted Firmware
CA	Certificate Authority
CPU	Central Processing Unit
DoS	Denial of Service
DRAM	Dynamic Read-Only Memory
EPC	Enclave Page Cache
EPCM	Enclave Page Cache Map
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IETF	Internet Engineering Task Force
ITEE	Isolated Trusted Execution Environment
MEE	Memory Encryption Engine
MMU	Memory Management Unit
MPU	Memory Protection Unit
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer
OS	Operating System
PCR	Platform Configuration Registers
PRM	Processor Reserved Memory
REE	Rich Execution Environment
ROM	Read-Only Memory
RISE	Research Institutes of Sweden
TA	Trusted Application
TAM	Trusted Application Manager
TCB	Trusted Computing Base
TEE	Trusted Execution Environment
TEEP	Trusted Execution Environment Platform
TOC	Time-of-Check
TOU	Time-of-Use
SEV	Secure Encrypted Virtualization
SGX	Software Guard Extensions
SoC	System-on-Chip
CA	Certificate Authority
CPU	Central Processing Unit
DoS	Denial of Service
DRAM	Dynamic Read-Only Memory

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EPC	Enclave Page Cache
EPCM	Enclave Page Cache Map
IETF	Internet Engineering Task Force
ITEE	Isolated Trusted Execution Environment
MEE	Memory Encryption Engine
MMU	Memory Management Unit
MPU	Memory Protection Unit
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer
OS	Operating System
PCR	Platform Configuration Registers
PRM	Processor Reserved Memory

Table 3: Glossary

4 Introduction

Cloud platforms for private data *concern* businesses, individuals and public organisations such as those found in the healthcare sector. European organizations typically choose *on-premises* or *private* cloud-based solutions due to confidentiality and integrity issues around their stored data. The EU has stringent laws regarding personal data storage and its management, such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) introduced in 2018.

However, computing is **moving to span multiple environments**, from on-premises to public cloud to edge. As companies move to these environments, they need protection controls for sensitive IP and workload data and are increasingly seeking greater assurances and more transparency of these controls.

ASCLEPIOS is an EU-financed security-focused research project towards *confidential computing* for the healthcare sector. The field of confidential computing emerged in response to the concerns about the security of data on commodity operating systems and the trust towards cloud service providers, inherent in the cloud computing model. Confidential computing aims to enable deployment and execution of workloads on remote platforms in secure environments isolated from both cloud system administration tools and from other collocated processes.

Confidential computing is based on *isolated trusted execution environments* (ITEEs). One realisation of ITEEs is *hardware-based trusted execution environments* (TEEs). The TEE is isolated from the Rich Execution Environment (REE) where the untrusted Operating System (OS) runs. The REE resources are accessible from the TEE, while the TEE resources are not from the REE, unless explicitly allowed. Therefore, only trusted resources can access other trusted resources.

One example is **Intel Software Guard Extensions** (SGX), while others include the AEGIS (the first one in 2003), or IBMs SecureBlue++, or the AMD Secure Encrypted Virtualization (SEV) [1], [2], [3], [4], [5]. The idea is that application developers can execute their programs on CPUs *where other programs exist* which may be untrusted or in the worst case malicious. Essentially the idea is instruction code and data isolation on protected areas on the chip, using encryption. Should data be read, it will be in an encrypted form. Decryption is done on the fly.

Intel **SGX** (Intel Software Guard Extensions) offers hardware-based memory encryption that isolates specific application code and data in memory. SGX allows user-level code to allocate private regions of memory, called *enclaves*

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which are designed to be protected from processes running at higher privilege levels¹. Enclaves can be used to run security and privacy-sensitive workloads in isolation on remote platforms. This helps reduce the trust required from the operator of the computing platform and provides additional tools for compliance and security assurance. These properties make ITEEs particularly suitable for protecting data in e-health systems. Therefore, task T4.1 *addresses the protocols for secure management of enclave workloads*. The whole suite of security protocols is considered, including key, firmware patch and workload management for ITEEs.

Figure 1: Conceptual view of a TEE

4.1 Scope

This document introduces background on the principles and functioning of Trusted Execution Environments (TEEs) and the Trusted Execution Environment architecture and protocol for workload management in TEEs. Both the architecture and protocol are on-going standardization efforts in the Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF). The purpose of the document is to communicate principles behind the functioning of several types of TEEs and the proposed generic approach to deploying workloads in TEEs. Therefore, the document has only an *informational* purpose. The focus on protocol and architecture standardization activities aligns the document with the implementation activities planned within the

¹ <https://www.intel.com/content/www/us/en/architecture-and-technology/software-guard-extensions.html>

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ASCLEPIOS project. As a result, enclave workload management software implemented to support the ASCLEPIOS project will be largely following the architecture and protocol introduced by this document.

4.2 Objectives

The primary objectives of this document are to:

- Describe the principles and functioning of Trusted Execution Environments (TEEs).
- Describe the Trusted Execution Environment Platform (TEEP) Architecture standardization work;
- Describe the protocol for workload management in TEEs supporting the TEEP Architecture.
- Indicate how an implementation of the Trusted Execution Environment Architecture can support the ASCLEPIOS platform.

4.3 Relation to Other Work Packages and Deliverables

This deliverable is tightly coupled with other deliverables in Work Package (WP) 4, as well as with work in other WPs of the ASCLEPIOS project. When it comes to other deliverables in WP4, this document introduces the background on the principles and functioning of Trusted Execution Environments (TEEs) and the Trusted Execution Environment architecture and protocol for workload management in TEEs. Further deliverables in WP4 will build on this background to address important aspects essential for the security of workloads in TEEs. In particular, deliverable D4.2 will complement the TEEP architecture with a view of *workload attestation* – including an attestation architecture and related artefacts. Deliverable D4.3 will expand this foundation with an exploration of the inter-operability of between different types of TEEs as well as the portability of the workloads between the different types of TEEs.

In relation to other WPs of the ASCLEPIOS project, this deliverable is most directly related to WP5, in particular tasks T5.2 and T5.3, which will contain RISE's implementation of components and protocols for workload management in TEEs, according to the architecture described in this document.

5 Security guarantees of ITEEs

In the context of the ASCLEPIOS project, we consider isolated trusted execution environments that fulfill the following security requirements:

- *Isolation from other components*
- *Protected communication channels*
- *Mechanisms to verify the integrity of code, data and communication channels*
- *Secure and trusted boot*

This allows the ITEE to operate under an attacker model where a malicious party could have the following capabilities:

- *The attacker may control all software components in the system except a Trusted Computing Base (TCB). This could, for example, include the OS and other software.*
- *The attacker can intercept, modify and redirect communication between different entities*
- *The attacker can perform protocol-level attacks but cannot break cryptographic primitives*
- *The attacker can read and modify memory contents that reside in external memory and external storage (physical attacks).*

Figure 2: Example of a simple trusted execution environment where a trusted application runs in a separate space

Under this attacker model, we generally exclude denial-of-service attacks. Furthermore, while we may consider physical attacks against external components, we do not consider physical attacks against the CPU/SoC itself. The rationale behind this is that attacking external

components is relatively easy, since the attacker can, for example, intercept data over a communication bus or simply swap an external component with a bogus one, while physical attacks against a modern CPU is more complex and requires access to relatively expensive hardware [6]. Next, we discuss how the requirements for the ITEE is met.

5.1 Isolation

A central assumption regarding ITEEs is that the trusted application (TA) executes within barriers that separate it from any other software in the system (bar the TCB). The objective is to prohibit direct manipulation of the trusted application by non-trusted entities. Let us briefly look into three important types: spatial, temporal and cryptographic isolation.

5.1.1 Spatial isolation

Spatial isolation separates components in memory (i.e. space). This is often provided by a memory protection or memory management unit (MPU / MMU), which in the case of a trusted execution environment has often been enhanced to increase security.

Figure 3: Isolation of enclaves in Intel SGX.

For example, Intel SGX behaves as a secondary MPU to the primary MMU and prohibits direct access to a small memory region reserved for enclaves and metadata [1].

More specifically, the CPU itself contains the Processor Reserved Memory (PRM), which holds Enclave Page Cache (EPC) and Enclave Page Cache Map (EPCM). The former hold enclave code and data while the latter is used to hold metadata for pages in EPC and external memory. Since EPC is very small, the CPU uses the external memory to cache enclave pages in and out (similar to how an OS would use a swap file). To protect enclave memory from unauthorized access, pages are transparently encrypted by the Memory Encryption Engine (MEE) as they leave the CPU.

5.1.2 Temporal separation

Temporal separation isolates components in time. For example, in a real-time operating system, temporal separation could mean execution time and latency guarantees for each task. In an ITEE this could instead mean minimizing the effects of multiple applications (trusted or not) sharing the same hardware.

An example of a hardware mechanism for temporal isolation is the ARMv8 timer hierarchy. Using three dedicated physical timers with associated interrupts at corresponding priority levels, the OS can interrupt applications; the hypervisor can interrupt applications and the OS and finally, the TrustZone sub-system can interrupt applications, OS and the hypervisor.

5.1.3 Cryptographic separation

On a high level, in a cryptographically separated system, one may have access to data but will also need the correct cryptographic information to use this data.

An example of this is AMD SEV, which achieves spatial isolation partially by means of cryptographic separation. Each execution environment is placed inside a virtual machine, the memory of which is encrypted by a unique key. This key is not available to any application or even the CPU itself (only the Secure Processor and the Memory Controller can access these keys).

Figure 4: Transparent encryption of virtual machine memory in AMD SEV.

5.2 Communication

In theory, a trusted application could run in total isolation from other software. In practice, however, this is seldom (if ever) meaningful. In real-world applications, we often want trusted software to be isolated from the environment apart from a well-defined and controlled

communication channel. This allows the trusted application to communicate with its surroundings while minimizing the attack surface to possibly malicious counterparts. Consider for example, the ARM TrustZone, which executes trusted applications in the Secure World and other applications in the Normal World [4]. Untrusted applications must communicate with trusted applications via a special Monitor Call instruction (SMC) which behaves similar to a system call but calls into the TrustZone Monitor which is part of the TCB. After ensuring that the call meets the communication policy (e.g. the two parties are allowed to communicate) and has the required format it can be forwarded to a trusted application whose response will then be forwarded back to the caller. This creates a very narrow and well-defined hub for communication, which can be improved further by using a communication protocol such the GlobalPlatform call specification which allows transferring up to 4 parameters in each call in such way that correctness of memory pointer parameters can be controlled [7].

Figure 5: Inter-process communication between normal and trusted applications in GlobalPlatform.

5.3 Integrity and authenticity

According to our security model, an attacker can intercept and modify all communication. In addition, she is able to manipulate data at rest. Hence when communicating with a trusted application, we must verify the integrity and authenticity of the communication channel and its endpoint. Similarly, a trusted application needs to verify the integrity and authenticity of data it may have previously stored on external storage.

Normally one would solve both problems by using some secret knowledge (e.g. a private key) to protect the resource in question. In a trusted execution environment, we need to improve this further by ensuring that this knowledge cannot be easily stolen or faked. For example, the cryptographic data may be managed by some hardware TCB that prohibits access outside some (for this threat model) secure protocol.

5.4 Cryptographic separation for integrity and authenticity

A common approach to integrity and authenticity in trusted systems is to make use of cryptographic data (keys, certificates, reports) that are derived from the state of that system. If the system is in an invalid state (e.g. it has been infected by malware), the generated cryptographic data will differ from the expected one and the target will fail to communicate with legitimate entities. However, to achieve this in a secure fashion, one must provide mechanisms where the cryptographic data cannot be forged or stolen.

For example, Intel SGX uses hardware/firmware mechanisms not otherwise available to software (trusted or not) to:

1. Compute the state of the TCB and the enclaves
2. Use the state information + some public and private data to derive a new cryptographic data (see figure)
3. Depending on usage, this data may or may not leave the CPU.

Since this is mostly done in hardware, the software is given no opportunity to lie about its state.

Figure 6: SGX key derivation can be used to generate keys based on enclave or system state and/or operation and user parameters

Intel SGX uses this mechanism to provide local attestation, that is, an unforgeable report about the authenticity and integrity of an enclave. This can be enhanced further with remote attestation where the CPU proves to an external entity that it is indeed (1) some specific genuine Intel device and (2) it guarantees the authenticity of a trusted application currently running [1].

5.5 Boot

So far, we have discussed the security properties of an ITEE when active. However, in a trusted execution environment we also need to make guarantees about the state of the platform and the initial state of the system. In particular, we need to prove that the TCB has not been tampered with.

The boot sequence is normally a chain of operations that are responsible for different stages of the boot. This often starts with a trust anchor in the form of a secure ROM which has the

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cryptographic data to verify the next stage. A good example of this is the Arm Trusted Firmware (ATF) reference implementation [8]:

Figure 7: ATF boot sequence.

5.6 Breaking the trust chain

In early versions of AMD-SEV the trust chain could be broken, rendering the ITEE insecure. The problem was essentially that an early stage in the boot chain failed to properly authenticate the next stage, allowing an attacker to supply his own modified firmware [9].

Figure 8: Broken trust chain in early AMD SEV implementations.

This is an example of a security issue that affects ITEE. In the next chapter we will discuss such issues in more detail.

6 Known ITEE vulnerabilities and mitigations

The sensitive nature of an ITEE requires it to work securely at all times. A security vulnerability in an ITEE or related component is often considered an extremely critical security problem. Nevertheless, there exist multiple security issues in the past and current generation ITEE technologies. In this chapter, we will take a look at some such vulnerabilities and discuss possible mitigations.

The main body of known ITEE vulnerabilities could be divided into the following classes:

- software implementation vulnerabilities
- hardware vulnerabilities
- side-channel attacks
- physical attacks

6.1 Software vulnerabilities

Standard software issues such as buffer overflow and Time-of-Check / Time of Use (TOC/TOU) bugs [10, 11] can also manifest in ITEE implementations. Software bugs are in fact, the most common source of security vulnerabilities in ITEEs. Consider, for example, the following list of recent software security bugs, covering almost the entire ITEE landscape:

- CVE-2017-5691: inadequate protection of system resources allows an attacker to break the trust anchor provided by Intel SGX.
- CVE-2019-9836: insecure implementation elliptic-curve cryptography in the Secure Processor allows SEV key recovery
- CVE-2017-16837: uncontrolled pointers in Intel's trusted boot allows malicious users to overwrite PCR registers of a TPM
- CVE-2017-6292: NVIDIA TLZ TrustZone implementation contains an integer overflow that allows an attacker to write to otherwise inaccessible memory locations
- CVE-2015-9073: Qualcomm QSEE TrustZone implementation contains a NULL pointer de-reference bug that allows an attacker to access otherwise inaccessible memory locations.
- CVE-2017-3893: in QNX SDP implementation and configuration errors may allow an attacker to modify the virtual memory configuration to gain full access to the memory.
- CVE-2017-12188: in Linux KVM, a path traversal error allows a malicious guest to execute arbitrary code on the host OS.
- CVE-2017-4901: a buffer error in VMWare Workstation and Fusion allows a malicious guest to execute arbitrary code on the host OS.
- CVE-2019-5736: inadequate self-protection allows an attacker to break out of a Docker container and gain root access on the host.

To reduce software insecurities, we recommend that developers do the following:

- Follow standard secure software development practices.
- Minimize the size of the TCB.

- Follow the principle of least privilege.
- Provide mechanisms to securely update a vulnerable ITEE.

In addition, each platform and each technology is only secure under a set of assumptions. It is important that trusted application developers are aware of these assumptions otherwise seemingly secure code can turn out to be insecure. See for example [12].

6.2 Hardware vulnerabilities

Dedicated hardware functions are often used to improve the security of ITEEs. For example, the CPU may ensure that certain privileged instruction can only be used in some trusted states or provide mechanisms to separate different software components in memory. Normally such hardware functions play a central role in the security of the system and if broken or bypassed the entire system may be left vulnerable.

While not as common as software vulnerabilities, a significant number of ITEE hardware vulnerabilities have been discovered in recent years. Some notable examples are

- CVE-2015-0565: Rowhammer - exploits charge leakages between adjacent memory cells in DRAM to read and modify sensitive memory contents
- CVE-2017-5753: Spectre - exploits effects of speculative execution on branch prediction to retrieve sensitive data
- CVE-2017-5754: Meltdown - exploits effects of speculative execution on caches to retrieve sensitive data
- CVE-2018-3620: Foreshadow - exploits effects of speculative execution on caches to retrieve sensitive data
- CVE-2018-12126: Fallout - exploits effects of speculative execution on store buffers to retrieve sensitive data
- CVE-2019-11091: Zombieload - exploits effects of speculative execution on unreachable memory to retrieve sensitive data

In theory, the hardware is fixed and hardware vulnerabilities cannot be corrected. In practice, some of what we consider hardware is firmware and microcode that can be updated. Furthermore, hardware vulnerabilities may sometimes be avoided by modifying system software to use hardware in a different way (or not use it at all). For example, consider the fixes provided for the Spectre and Meltdown vulnerabilities [13], [14].

To avoid future hardware vulnerabilities, we recommend designers to do the following:

- Follow standard secure development practices.
- Minimize hardware re-use between security domains (see next section on side channels).
- Follow the principle of least privilege.
- Provide mechanisms to securely update a vulnerable system.

6.3 Side-channel attacks

A trusted execution environment is normally tailored to prohibit unauthorized parties from direct access to its resources. For example, an untrusted application should not be able to examine memory contents of a trusted application. It may, however, be possible to indirectly access such information from side channels which are indirect sources of information. For example, by analysing execution time or power usage of a trusted application, an attacker may be able to deduce information that was not directly accessible.

In the case of ITEE, hardware components shared between secure and insecure domains are often the main source of information leakage [15]. In particular, the memory cache and related subsystems in the CPU are known to be a common source of catastrophic side-channel vulnerabilities. In fact, most of the hardware vulnerabilities discussed earlier are actually side-channel vulnerabilities that exploit shared caches and other shared hardware [16], [17], [18], [19], [20].

The standard recommendations for combating side-channel vulnerabilities are:

- Remove or minimize the information leakage.
- Minimize the correlation between leaked data and sensitive data.

For example, one could utilize cache-colouring to minimize cache side-channel leakage (for example, Sanctum [21]) or introduce noise and ambiguities in the branch predictor to minimize channel correlation to sensitive data (see for example [22] and [23]).

6.4 Physical attacks

Physical attacks are normally ignored during security analyses as most systems are vulnerable to physical attacks in some degree. But in the case of trusted execution - especially in a foreign cloud environment - an exception should be made.

Our main assumption is that a malicious entity with temporary physical access to the device (i.e. the Evil Maid attack [24]) is able to modify certain components to affect the security of the system:

1. Extract contents of the RAM (but not the memory inside to the CPU)
2. Read and modify software and firmware on external storage
3. Read and modify firmware and configurations on on-board memory (e.g. BIOS flash)
4. Replace a sensitive component with a malicious counterfeit

Mitigations for withstanding such attacks may include

1. Encrypt and authenticate external memory used by the ITEE (1)
2. Encrypt and authenticate data at rest used by the ITEE (2, 3)
3. Use secure and trusted boot to authenticate the entire boot chain including firmware and configurations (2, 3)
4. When possible, sensitive hardware components such as TPM and HSM should make use of an internal secret to prove their authenticity.

7 Protocols for key, firmware and workload management

An isolated trusted execution environment (ITEE) on its own is not useful unless it can be integrated in the wider context of an enterprise system. This requires mechanisms to manage workloads in an ITEE instance. Workload management includes actions to deploy and update, start and stop the workload process, as well as clean up once the workload is not necessary or must be removed due to licensing considerations [28-31].

Firmware management is another important aspect. While ITEEs rely heavily on hardware features for memory and execution isolation, they also rely on firmware components that expose or control such features. Similar to workloads in ITEEs, the firmware on platforms running ITEEs must be updated to enable new features or patched whenever vulnerabilities are discovered [32]. Unlike workload management, platform firmware is deployed already at production time and is not normally removed from a platform until decommissioning.

Once workload code and data are deployed to ITEEs, their integrity needs to be validated to guarantee that they were not modified, maliciously or accidentally. This is called attestation and is often a crucial part of any ITEE architecture. A closely related step is to provision cryptographic material to workloads in ITEEs or sign a certificate containing the public key of the ITEE instance, and sometimes follows the attestation step. This allows to set up a secure communication channel between the workload running in the ITEE and either other similar workloads or the rest of the enterprise system. The rest of this section contains a review of the existing approaches for key, firmware and workload management in ITEEs as well as on-going work in this area.

7.1 Trusted Execution Environment Platform Architecture

While early versions of trustworthy computing hardware have existed for over two decades, they could only execute fixed functions defined at production (or even specification) time. ITEEs capable to run code deployed at run-time have been introduced recently and are yet to achieve widespread industry adoption. As a result, approaches to manage the ITEE firmware, workloads and key material are still under active research. On the other hand, on-going standardization efforts aim to define the architecture and communication protocols of infrastructure for the management of ITEE workloads² and remote attestation of ITEE workloads³. This deliverable focuses on the management of workloads for ITEEs, while aspects of workload attestation are addressed in the upcoming deliverable D4.2. The workload management mechanism described in this document is based on the architecture document⁴ (currently work in progress) of the Trusted Execution Environment Provisioning (TEEP) working group of the Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF). Within the ASCLEPIOS project, RISE contributed to the TEEP architecture document in the form of feedback and comments.

2 Trusted Execution Environment Provisioning (teep) <https://datatracker.ietf.org/wg/teep/about/>

3 Remote ATtestation ProcedureS (rats) IETF group <https://datatracker.ietf.org/wg/rats/about/>

4 Trusted Execution Environment Provisioning (TEEP) Architecture <https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/draft-ietf-teep-architecture/>

Several entities are present throughout the ITEE workload lifecycle management. We next outline these entities:

- *Service Provider* and *Devices Administrators* manage workloads deployed to ITEEs. Device Administrators interact with devices hosting ITEEs directly or through an intermediate component, while Service Providers interact with devices hosting ITEEs only indirectly through dedicated intermediate components to help scalability.
- A *Trusted Application Manager* is the intermediate component that service providers and device administrators use to manage workloads deployed to ITEEs - either on a specific device or on large numbers of devices controlled by the respective *Service Provider* or *Device Administrator*. The *Trusted Application Manager* performs workload management tasks through the instance of a *TEEP Broker* installed on devices hosting ITEEs. To ensure compatibility with network restrictions (such as firewalls and network address translation), the *Trusted Application Manager* does not contact the TEEP
- A *TEEP Broker* runs on the device and enables message protocol exchange between the *Trusted Application Manager* and the ITEE on the device. The *TEEP Broker* does not terminate messages, it simply relays them the TEEP agent (described below).
- A *TEEP Agent* is a component running inside the ITEE and receiving messages from the *Trusted Application Manager*. The *TEEP Agent* sends a reply to the *Trusted Application Manager* both in the case when the *TEEP Agent* itself is the destination, as well as when the *TEEP Agent* forwards the message to the workload running inside the ITEE.
- The *Certification Authority* is an entity trusted by all components described above. It issues or signs root certificates for all components described above; some of the root certificates signed by the certification authority (called *Trust Anchors*) are embedded into the ITEE either at production time or at a later stage. Trust anchors are essential for remote attestation of workloads running in ITEEs. Workload attestation is covered in deliverable D4.2.

Figure 9: Relation between the TEEP architecture components.

The architecture can be implemented using the Open Trust Protocol (under standardization at IETF). The Open Trust Protocol is tailored to the requirements of the supporting ITEEs on heterogeneous devices. It is conceived as a generic protocol for payload delivery and deployment in ITEEs and can be used to deliver trusted applications supporting the ASCLEPIOS use cases into ITEEs on heterogeneous devices.

7.2 Security Considerations

From a security standpoint, the TEEP architecture relies on the security assumptions built into the design of the ITEEs. It does not attempt to address any security vulnerabilities of the ITEEs described above. Instead, it focuses on preserving the confidentiality and integrity of the communication between the developer or device administrator and the TEEP agent or the Trusted Applications. Below, we go through the security and trust model of the components of the TEEP architecture.

7.2.1 Broker Trust Model

The architecture enables the TAM to communicate, via a TEEP Broker, with the device's ITEE to manage TAs. All TAM messages are signed, and sensitive data is encrypted such that the TEEP Broker cannot modify or capture sensitive data. This reduces the risk of data leakage in case the TEEP Broker – that runs in a potentially vulnerable REE – is infected by malware.

The TEEP Agent running in the TEE is responsible for protecting against potential attacks from a compromised TEEP Broker or rogue malware in the REE. The TEEP Agent validates the signature of each TEEP protocol request and checks the signing certificate against its Trust Anchors. To mitigate Denial-of-Service (DoS) attacks [33-36], it might also add some protection scheme such as a threshold on repeated requests or number of TAs that can be

installed. This prevents a rogue TEEP Broker from sending corrupted data to the TEEP Agent, or launching a DoS attack by sending a flood of TEEP protocol requests.'

7.2.2 Compromised REE

The REE on a device may be compromised, enabling it to launch several types of DoS attacks. The compromised REE may terminate the TEEP Broker such that TEEP transactions cannot reach the TEE. However, while such a DoS attack cannot be prevented, the REE cannot access anything in the TEE if it is implemented correctly. While some TEEs have a watchdog scheme to observe REE state and mitigate DoS attacks against it, but most available TEEs do not have this capability. In other scenarios, a compromised REE may ask a TEEP Broker to make repeated requests to a TEEP Agent in a TEE to install or uninstall a TA. A TA installation or uninstallation request constructed by the TEEP Broker or REE will be rejected by the TEEP Agent because the request will not have the correct signature from a TAM to pass the request signature validation.

7.2.3 Compromised CA

A root CA for TAM certificates might get compromised. Some TEE Trust Anchor update mechanism is expected from device OEMs. TEEs are responsible for validating certificate revocation against a TAM certificate chain. If the root CA of some TEE device certificates is compromised, these devices might be rejected by a TAM. This is a decision of the TAM implementation and policy choice. TAMs are responsible for validating any intermediate CA for TEE device certificates.

7.2.4 Certificate Renewal

TEE device certificates are expected to be long-lived, longer than the lifetime of a device. A TAM certificate usually has a lifetime of 2 to 5 years. A TAM should get renewed or rekeyed certificates. The root CA certificates for a TAM, which are embedded into the Trust Anchor store in a device, should have long lifetimes that do not require device Trust Anchor update. On the other hand, it is imperative that OEMs or device providers plan for support of Trust Anchor update in their shipped devices.

7.2.5 Protocol details

The TEEP protocol consists of a couple of messages exchanged between a TAM and a TEEP Agent via a TEEP Broker. The messages are designed to provide end-to-end security. TEEP protocol messages are signed and where necessary encrypted by the endpoints, i.e., the TAM and the TEEP Agent. However, trusted applications may as well be encrypted and signed by the service provider.

7.2.5.1 Protocol Messages

The current specification (work in progress) defines six messages listed below:

1. A TAM queries a device's current state with a **QueryRequest** message.
2. A TEEP Agent will, after authenticating and authorizing the request, report attestation information, list all TAs, and provide information about supported algorithms and extensions in a **QueryResponse** message.
3. An **error message** is returned if the request could not be processed. A TAM will process the QueryResponse message and determine whether subsequent message exchanges to install, update, or delete trusted applications shall be initiated.
4. With the **TrustedAppInstall** message a TAM can instruct a TEEP Agent to install a TA. The TEEP Agent will process the message, determine whether the TAM is authorized and whether the TA has been signed by an authorized SP. In addition to the binary, the TAM may also provide personalization data. If the TrustedAppInstall message was processed successfully, then a Success message is returned to the TAM, an Error message otherwise.
5. With the **TrustedAppDelete** message, a TAM can instruct a TEEP Agent to delete one or multiple TA(s).
6. A **Success** message is returned when the operation has been completed successfully, and an Error message otherwise.

7.2.5.2 Error codes

The specification currently under definition lists the following error codes to notify of an error condition. We intend to further expand the error code list in case the prototype development and integration efforts within ASCLEPIOS reveal error conditions insufficiently described by the existing error codes. See the current list of error codes below:

- **ERR_ILLEGAL_PARAMETER**: The TEEP Agent sends this error message when a request contains incorrect fields or fields that are inconsistent with other fields.
- **ERR_UNSUPPORTED_EXTENSION**: The TEEP Agent sends this error message when it recognizes an unsupported extension or unsupported message.
- **ERR_REQUEST_SIGNATURE_FAILED**: The TEEP Agent sends this error message when it fails to verify the signature of the message.
- **ERR_UNSUPPORTED_MSG_VERSION**: The TEEP Agent receives a message but does not support the indicated version.
- **ERR_UNSUPPORTED_CRYPTO_ALG**: The TEEP Agent receives a request message encoded with an unsupported cryptographic algorithm.
- **ERR_BAD_CERTIFICATE**: The TEEP Agent returns this error when processing of a certificate failed. For diagnosis purposes it is RECOMMENDED to include information about the failing certificate in the error message.
- **ERR_UNSUPPORTED_CERTIFICATE**: The TEEP Agent returns this error when a certificate was of an unsupported type.

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- **ERR_CERTIFICATE_REVOKED:** The TEEP Agent returns this error when a certificate was revoked by its signer.
- **ERR_CERTIFICATE_EXPIRED:** The TEEP Agent returns this error when a certificate has expired or is not currently valid.
- **ERR_INTERNAL_ERROR:** The TEEP Agent returns this error when a miscellaneous internal error occurred while processing the request.
- **ERR_RESOURCE_FULL:** This error is reported when a device resource is not available anymore, such as storage space is full.
- **ERR_TA_NOT_FOUND:** This error will occur when the target TA does not exist. This error may happen when the TAM has stale information and tries to delete a TA that has already been deleted.
- **ERR_TA_ALREADY_INSTALLED:** While installing a TA, a TEE will return this error if the TA has already been installed.
- **ERR_TA_UNKNOWN_FORMAT:** The TEEP Agent returns this error when it does not recognize the format of the TA binary.
- **ERR_TA_DECRYPTION_FAILED:** The TEEP Agent returns this error when it fails to decrypt the TA binary.
- **ERR_TA_DECOMPRESSION_FAILED:** The TEEP Agent returns this error when it fails to decompress the TA binary.
- **ERR_MANIFEST_PROCESSING_FAILED:** The TEEP Agent returns this error when manifest processing failures occur that are less specific than **ERR_TA_UNKNOWN_FORMAT**, **ERR_TA_UNKNOWN_FORMAT**, and **ERR_TA_DECOMPRESSION_FAILED**.
- **ERR_PD_PROCESSING_FAILED:** The TEEP Agent returns this error when it fails to process the provided personalization data.

7.3 Protocol support for the ASCLEPIOS platform

Within the ASCLEPIOS project, the TEEP protocol definition and prototype implementation will support deployment of trusted applications on server platforms in cloud environments. In particular, the TEEP protocol will support the ASCLEPIOS use cases by providing a scalable and usable approach to deploy key management libraries (“*Key tray*”) developed within work package 2 and integrated into the ASCLEPIOS platform in WP5. Moreover, TEEs will be used to run the ABE Master entity that will be responsible for the generation of the ABE keys.

As described in Deliverable 2.2, KeyTray is a key storage that exists in the CSP and stores ciphertexts of all the symmetric keys that have been generated by various data owners and are needed in order to decrypt data. Every registered user can contact the KeyTray directly and request access to the stored ciphertexts. Furthermore, the symmetric keys are encrypted with a CP- ABE scheme. Thus, a single symmetric key is encrypted only once and users with certain access rights and different keys are able to access it (i.e. decrypt it). Moreover, similar to MS, KeyTray is also TEE-enabled and is running in an enclave called the KeyTray Enclave [27].

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The *Key Tray* component is essential for maintaining the security of the ASCLEPIOS platform, through ensuring the confidentiality and integrity of cryptographic material. While the platform relies on the implementation and use of novel cryptographic approaches (a combination of secure searchable encryption and attribute-based encryption), security of encryption keys and authentication credentials remains a keystone for the security of the healthcare data.

8 Conclusion

In this deliverable, we have provided an overview of the principles of isolated trusted execution environments (ITEEs), including ITEE security guarantees, as well as known vulnerabilities and mitigations. We further introduced some relevant standardization work done regarding key and workload management of ITEEs. In particular, we focus on artefacts produced by the Trusted Execution Environment Platform IETF working group, including the TEEP architecture and the open trust protocol implementing the architecture. The material in this document is intended to support developers and designers in implementing trusted applications that are both secure and compliant to on-going standardization work. Within project ASCLEPIOS, this document will be complemented in the following tasks with an overview of attestation protocols for ITEEs and an exploration of the interoperability of ITEEs.

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